

BASED ON SOCIAL COOPERATION PEDAGOGICAL OF STUDENTS IMPROVING THEIR SKILLS METHODS

Abjalova Hilola Raxmat qizi

Trainee teacher of Termiz State University

<https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10651132>

Abstract: Cooperative teaching technology is the knowledge of every student that he realizes that his success leads to the success of the group, independent and to diligently work intellectually, acquire knowledge, complete educational assignments and quality performance, thorough mastering of educational material, partner to his comrades information was given about preparing the ground for mutual exchange of ideas. In the article, the formation of social activity skills in students motivation and the role of motivation and their implementation its importance has been researched on a scientific basis.

Key words: Motivation, social activity, concept of personality, humanitarianism, educational processes, social activity, reading, learning, pedagogical processes, method, approach, improvement.

Annotatsiya: Hamkorlikda o'qitish texnologiyasi har bir talabaning bilim olishdagi muvafaqqiyati guruh muvafaqqiyatiga olib kelishini anglashini, mustaqil va sidqidildan aqliy mehnat qilishga, bilim olishga, o'quv topshiriqlarini to'liq va sifatli bajarishga o'quv materialini puxta o'zlashtirishga, o'rtoqlariga hamkor bo'lib, o'zaro fikr almashishga zamin tayyorlashi haqida ma'lumot berilib o'tildi. Maqolada talabalarda ijtimoiy faollik ko'nikmalarini shakllantirishda motivlashtirish va motivatsiyaning o'rnini hamda ularni amaliyotga tatbiq etishning ahamiyati ilmiy asoslangan holda tadqiq etilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Motivatsiya, ijtimoiy faollik, shaxs tushunchasi, insonparvarlik, bilim-tarbiya jarayonlari, ijtimoiy faoliyat, o'qish, o'rganish, pedagogik jarayonlar, metod, yondashuv, takomillashtirish.

Аннотация: Технология кооперативного обучения – это знания каждого ученика. что он осознает, что его успех ведет к успеху группы, независимой и усердно работать интеллектуально, приобретать знания, выполнять учебные задания и качественное исполнение, доскональное усвоение учебного материала, партнер своих товарищей была дана информация о подготовке почвы для взаимного обмена идеями. В статье формирование навыков социальной активности у студентов. мотивация и роль мотивации и их реализация его важность исследована на научной основе.

Ключевые слова: Мотивация, социальная активность, концепция личности, гуманизм, образовательные процессы, социальная активность, чтение, обучение, педагогические процессы, метод, подход, совершенствование.

Introduction: creative models of improving the mechanism of preparing students for social life are being implemented in world educational institutions based on cooperative pedagogy. Systematic work on preparing students for social life, developing emotional, mental and physical abilities based on cooperative activities, improving flexibility and joint actions of subjects, and the process of preparing students for social life on the basis of cooperative pedagogy in scientific research institutions scientific researches are being carried out on designing based on an innovative approach, developing technologies for preparing future teachers for certain professional activities, implementing pedagogical and psychological values in the process of achieving professional maturity.

Literature analysis: researches are being conducted on global information flows and acceleration, development of students' professional abilities from science and technology development, preparation of future pedagogues for innovative professional activities, improvement of pedagogical cooperation models, expansion of pedagogical and psychological possibilities of preparing students for social life.

The analysis of pedagogical literature and a number of scientific studies of recent years allows us to assume that the adaptation of students in the study group should include the goals, principles, factors, stages, methods and organizational forms of pedagogical accompaniment activities.

Because the goal of any pedagogical process is to predict the results of the student's interaction with teachers in the form of generalized mental images, based on which all other components of this process are selected, interconnected and built. The theoretical analysis and generalization of the experience of our professional activity, as well as the results of the emphatic experience, made it possible to base and develop a model of pedagogical support for the adaptation of students in the study group. The interaction in the group is not about itself, but about the content of the curriculum of academic subjects, visions of the future profession, discussion of the participation of the group in the proposed forms of activities outside the auditorium, the higher educational institution in general. and in particular, it is formed on the basis of dedication to the life of a particular faculty (institute).

In this case, supporting constructive forms of interaction, gathering experience of effective intergroup interaction, providing individual assistance in overcoming difficulties in the adaptation process, and preventing conflicts become the main directions of pedagogical activity. Thus, the integration of the educational resources of the higher educational institution and the socio-cultural environment is the main direction of the accompanying activity, and it allows the comprehensive use of a wide range of social-psychological-pedagogical work methods and forms. The process of pedagogical support of the student's adaptation in the study group includes several stages: 1st stage - propaedeutic - diagnostic. It refers to the preparation and entry into the process of adaptation of all participants of pedagogical accompaniment: both those who accompany and those who are accompanied. The duration of this stage is 6-8 weeks.

The step-by-step algorithm of actions at this stage is as follows: training of teachers and tutors of first-year study groups, development of a one-year adaptation program by group tutors, tutor familiarization with students' personal work, organization of acquaintance with students in the study group, every to determine the adaptation potential of a group participant, to determine the factors that help students to adapt successfully in this study group. Stage 2 - gathering experience of constructive interaction in the group is the main thing. It is a field of social experiments where students have the opportunity to try different options of self-realization in the system of relations within the group under the guidance of teachers and senior students (who participate as tutors). The stage lasts 6 months. The algorithm of step-by-step actions is as follows: organization of training of constructive communication methods in the group by the tutor, regular work on the formation of the team in the group, creation of interaction situations that require the manifestation of the individual's different personal characteristics in the group and his communicative potential , analyzing the results of interaction within the group, then the algorithm can be repeated: organizing the training of new groups of skills and abilities, in particular, the student demonstrates these skills, analyzes and re-understands his activity and communication in the group create possible realistic situations.

Stage 3 - summarizing the results of the student's adaptation in the group, independent and expert assessment, linking these achievements with the results of educational activities, participation in extracurricular activities, identifying difficulties, further development of the student and the member of this educational group envisages the development of individual trajectories. The stage lasts 4-6 weeks. Algorithm of step-by-step actions - self-analysis, analysis in microgroups, general group analysis and reflection (re-understanding), organization of individual reflection meetings with the tutor. In order to achieve the goal of pedagogical accompaniment to the adaptation of students in the study group, the main forms of

traditional information giving (social-psychological, pedagogical support, organization of joint activities), methods (educational situations, actualization, strengthening and enrichment, assistance and design of creativity) and a wide range (individual and group conversations, discussions, collective-creative works, situational games, etc.) were used. It is suggested to use interactive adaptive teaching methods as part of the implementation of the pedagogical accompaniment model.

In order to effectively implement the adaptation process, active and interactive forms of training are used depending on the complexity of the educational process: elementary level - normative-logical and communicative; innovative projects; application and implementation of methods of modeling life situations. Game methods, the naming of complexity, role-playing, business game, technology of project communication, the social and psychological condition of the student in the study group, the student's ability to overcome difficulties, his success in his educational activities and the formation and development of perceptions about the chosen profession expands its potential for Strategic, tactical and operational monitoring of units is as follows: - strategic monitoring includes a set of diagnostic tools that allow studying the conditions for adapting students, determining the goals and tasks of accompaniment. This strategic monitoring is carried out with the help of a priori ranking of factors that influence the process of adaptation in the student's study group. - tactical monitoring with the help of a set of diagnostic tools that allow monitoring the level of adaptation of students, their orientation to group interaction, the need for standardized test methods, as well as quantitative and qualitative monitoring of the dynamics of changes, It is ensured by the analysis of the mastery.

- rapid monitoring performs the function of step-by-step monitoring of the effectiveness of passing the stages of pedagogical accompaniment to the adaptation of students in the study group.

It mainly includes express-diagnostic methods that allow you to quickly get feedback indicating the success/failure of one or another pedagogical effect.

Observation, analysis of student activity products, short interviews, results of reflexive interviews, express surveys, independent observation diaries are used for this purpose. The following rules are defined as the criteria for the effectiveness of pedagogical support for the adaptation of students in the study group: - the educational process of students and their academic and personal achievements in activities outside the auditorium; - satisfaction with the educational process at the higher educational institution for the chosen profession; a positive attitude towards one's study group expressed in the definition of "we" in the personal perception of the group; - methodological support for the accompanying process; - request for accompaniment by students. The result of successful accompaniment to the adaptation process is as follows: - the student learns the requirements, norms and rules of behavior in a new environment; - experiences psychological satisfaction when communicating with a new social environment; - students interact with other students and teachers; - the person is directed to the system of social relations in the higher educational institution. In this way, the model of pedagogical accompaniment in the adaptation of students to the study group clearly demonstrates the essence and content of the studied process. Its main task is not an expert assessment of the student's adaptation from the outside, but to encourage the student to understand the adaptation tasks facing him, the problems that arise in establishing and maintaining constructive relations with teammates. Therefore, companionship is, firstly, a general and integrated, and, moreover, a general system of support and assistance in the process of comprehensive activity; secondly, integrative - innovative technology, the improvement of its fundamental basis and the actualization of self-development activities, in addition, creating the necessary conditions for its disclosure and, as a result, the fulfillment of the main functions of an individual; and thirdly, it is a special relationship process between those who accompany and those who need help.

Tahlil va natija. Talabalarni o‘quv guruhiga moslashtirishning texnologik xaritasini tuzishda maqsadli blok ishlab chiqiladi. Maqsadli blokning vazifalari quyidagicha: - talabanning ta’sir obyekti pozitsiyasidan guruh ichidagi munosabatlar sub’ekti pozitsiyasiga o‘tishda pedagogik yondashuv jihatidan boshqarishni amalga oshirish; - birinchi kurs talabalarini tavsiya etilgan guruhiy faoliyat turlariga kiritish; - kursdoshlar bilan sheriklik, o‘zaro munosabatlarga ko‘maklashish va hamrohlik qilish. Bunda taxminiy tadbirlar rejasi ishlab chiqiladi, unda talabalarning o‘quv guruhida moslashuviga pedagogik hamrohlik qilishning barcha asosiy g‘oyalari aks ettirilgan bo‘ladi.

It is important to ensure that the same upbringing of children continues in educational organizations. It is expedient to pay special attention to this during training in activity centers organized in pre-school educational organizations. After all, it is important for children to grow up well, and for their future relationships to be creative.¹

The method was started in the early 20th century by the Italian physician Maria Montessori, who developed his theories through scientific experiments with his students; this method was used in public and private schools in many parts of the world.²

Conclusions and recommendations: To sum up, education of the young generation in the spirit of social activity is one of the urgent tasks of today. The emergence and understanding of behavior. A complete understanding of written actions is how the action was performed under the influence of a tool understanding and the methods and results of the implementation of this action are determined in

¹ Prator Saidmurad Irgashovich “PEDAGOGICAL MECHANISMS OF FINDING FEELINGS OF TOLERANCE IN CHILDREN DURING GAME ACTIVITY” Results of National Scientific Research International Journal 2023 . 159\163 6

² Bobokulova Nazokat Yusufovna “PROCESSES OF THE WORLDWIDE EXPANSION OF THE MONTESSORI METHOD” Results of National Scientific Research International Journal 2023 . 193\200 6

advance. Thus, we can think about the success of the implementation of the model of pedagogical accompaniment to the adaptation of students in the study group with the help of the included observation, the results of the students' activities, and the methods of assessing their mastery levels. But for scientific conclusions, it is required to provide monitoring data that confirms the observed trends quantitatively and qualitatively.

Used literature

1. Сергейчик С.И. Факторы гражданской социализации учащейся молодежи.//Журнал «Социологические исследования», 2002, май. – С.107-111.
2. Bobokulova Nazokat Yusufovna “PROCESSES OF THE WORLDWIDE EXPANSION OF THE MONTESSORI METHOD” Results of National Scientific Research International Journal 2023 . 193|200 б
3. Prator Saidmurad Irgashovich “PEDAGOGICAL MECHANISMS OF FINDING FEELINGS OF TOLERANCE IN CHILDREN DURING GAME ACTIVITY” Results of National Scientific Research International Journal 2023 . 159\163 б